

Clinical, Audiological and Psychological Profiles of Patients with Chronic Subjective Tinnitus: An Observational Study

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Abstract

Background: Chronic subjective tinnitus is a prevalent auditory symptom, often debilitating due to its subjective nature and the absence of a universal cure. The study aimed to evaluate the clinical, audiological and psychological profiles of patients with chronic subjective tinnitus with the objective of exploring correlations between tinnitus severity, audiological findings and psychological distress at a tertiary care hospital.

Methodology: A prospective observational study was conducted for a period of 18 months. A total of 100 patients with chronic subjective tinnitus participated. Following a thorough clinical history, audiometry and psychological assessments (Tinnitus Handicap Inventory, Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index) were done. Data was analyzed using descriptive statistics, Chi-square tests and paired t-tests.

Results: The majority of participants (61%) had tinnitus for less than a year. Sensorineural hearing loss was the most common audiological finding affecting over 60% of participants. Tinnitus severity correlated with psychological distress, with 32% reporting a moderate handicap. Sleep disturbances were common with 97% experiencing sleep difficulties and the most common etiologies were sensorineural hearing loss (22%) and presbycusis (18%).

Conclusion: Chronic subjective tinnitus is multifactorial with significant audiological and psychological impacts. Early detection and a holistic approach, combining audiological and psychological interventions are crucial for improving patient outcomes.

Keywords: Chronic Subjective Tinnitus, Sensorineural Hearing Loss, Psychological Distress, Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index, Tinnitus Handicap Inventory, Presbycusis.

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Introduction

Chronic subjective tinnitus defined as the perception of sound in the absence of an external source is a prevalent and often debilitating auditory symptom. Affecting up to 15% of the population, it is especially challenging due to its subjective nature, variability in clinical presentation, and the absence of a universal cure. Patients often report persistent ringing, buzzing, or hissing sounds that interfere with daily functioning and psychological

well-being. Though tinnitus is traditionally considered an audiological disorder, growing evidence suggests it is a complex neuro-auditory phenomenon often associated with both auditory dysfunction and psychological comorbidities. Interestingly, many individuals with chronic tinnitus show normal results on standard pure tone audiometry, leading to the hypothesis of "hidden hearing loss" involving synaptic damage or central

auditory pathway alterations that are not captured in conventional tests. [1] Advanced diagnostics like auditory brainstem response (ABR) and otoacoustic emissions have shown altered wave latencies and cochlear responses in such patients, indicating underlying pathophysiological changes.

Age and gender are key demographic variables influencing tinnitus characteristics. A large retrospective review found that patients over 40 years of age reported tinnitus to be louder, more annoying, and more distressing than their younger counterparts. [2] Women, in particular, were more likely to report heightened psychological distress associated with tinnitus, including increased tension, depression, and lower coping capacity. [3] These findings underline the necessity of considering age and gender specific factors when designing treatment plans.

Tinnitus severity is not solely determined by its acoustic characteristics but is significantly influenced by the psychological profile of the patient. Studies have shown that individuals with poor coping strategies tend to experience more distress from their tinnitus, regardless of its loudness. [4] In contrast, "high copers" demonstrate better psychological adjustment and report lower perceived severity.

Psychological testing using the Minnesota Multiphasic Personality Inventory (MMPI) has further reinforced these associations. Patients with tinnitus scored significantly higher in domains such as psychasthenia, hypochondriasis and social introversion compared to control groups, with these effects being more pronounced in women. [5] While the tinnitus may not be directly caused by psychological disorders, its chronic nature often leads to, or exacerbates, psychological symptoms.

Neurologically, chronic tinnitus is associated with altered cortical activity. Electroencephalographic (EEG) studies have shown that patients with severe tinnitus exhibit increased theta wave activity in the prefrontal cortex suggesting disrupted top down regulation of auditory inputs. [6] This supports the theory that chronic tinnitus involves maladaptive neuroplastic changes, making it both a perceptual and cognitive emotional phenomenon.

Another dimension of interest is the association between tinnitus and cognitive performance. Several studies have linked tinnitus with impairments in attention, memory, and information processing. In one neuropsychological assessment, patients performed poorly on digit span and visual recognition tasks, with the severity of deficits correlating positively with the duration and loudness of tinnitus. [7] This highlights the need for cognitive rehabilitation as part of a multidisciplinary management approach.

Audiologically, the degree of hearing loss especially in high frequencies has been positively correlated with tinnitus severity. A study found that patients with elevated high frequency hearing thresholds were more likely to report loud and long standing tinnitus. [8] These findings stress the importance of extended high frequency audiometry in early detection and prognosis.

The Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) instrument for psychiatric practice and research is easy to use and understand. Its simplicity as well as its ability to identify different groups of patients suggest several clinical and research applications in psychiatry and general medical settings. In a general clinical setting, the PSQI could be used to screen patients for the presence of significant sleep disturbances. [9]

Efforts to standardize the evaluation of tinnitus related distress have led to the development of tools such as the Tinnitus Handicap Inventory (THI) and the COMiT-ID framework. The latter identified "tinnitus intrusiveness", "sleep quality" and "sense of control" as critical outcomes for evaluating treatment effectiveness. [10,11] Such tools are essential in both clinical and research settings to measure and track patient centered outcomes.

Importantly, not all research supports the view of tinnitus as primarily a psychological disorder. A landmark study found that while many tinnitus sufferers do report emotional distress, the majority do not meet criteria for psychiatric illness. The authors argued that conventional psychological therapies may have limited benefit in such cases, and audiological interventions could be more effective. [12] This reinforces the need for individualized assessment and treatment.

In summary, chronic subjective tinnitus is a multifactorial condition with intertwined audiological, neurological and psychological components. A detailed understanding of patient profiles can help clinicians develop more effective, personalized treatment approaches. The study aimed to assess the clinical, audiological and psychological profiles of patients with chronic subjective tinnitus to identify common patterns, contributing factors, and the overall impact on daily functioning and quality of life.

Methodology

The prospective observational study was conducted over 18 months at a tertiary care hospital to evaluate the clinical, audiological, and psychological profiles of 100 adult patients with chronic subjective tinnitus. Participants aged 18 years and above with chronic subjective tinnitus who consented and complied with follow up were included.

Exclusion criteria were objective tinnitus, bedridden status, and major psychiatric illness, refusal to consent and follow up. Each underwent ENT evaluation, pure tone audiometry, and completed standardized questionnaires like the Tinnitus Handicap Inventory (THI) and Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) at baseline and after three months. Data was collected systematically and analyzed using descriptive statistics, Chi-square tests, and paired t-tests.

Ethical approval was obtained, written informed consent was taken and confidentiality was maintained.

Results

1. Duration of tinnitus: Most participants (61%) had tinnitus for less than one year, indicating early stage presentation in a majority of cases. Shorter duration may be linked to better treatment outcomes (Graph 1).

Graph 1: Distribution of study participants based on duration of tinnitus.

2. Types of hearing loss: Sensorineural hearing loss was the most common type, present in 69.23% (right ear) and 63.74% (left ear), suggesting cochlear or retrocochlear pathology was frequently associated with tinnitus (Graph 2).

Graph 2: Distribution of hearing loss among tinnitus patients based on pure tone audiometry.

3. Tinnitus Handicap Inventory (THI): A significant proportion of patients (32%) experienced a moderate handicap with THI scores improving post intervention, showing treatment effectiveness (Table 3).

Table 1: Grading of tinnitus related handicap based on Tinnitus Handicap Inventory (THI) Scores (N=100).

Grade	Handicap Level	n	%
1	Slight/No Handicap	25	25%
2	Mild Handicap	43	43%
3	Moderate Handicap	32	32%
4	Severe Handicap	0	0%
5	Catastrophic Handicap	0	0%
Total		100	100%

4. Sleep quality: Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI): Nearly all participants (97%) had some level of sleep difficulty with over 60% reporting moderate to severe disturbances, emphasizing tinnitus’ impact on sleep (Table 4).

Table 2: Sleep quality in study participants based on global Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) (N=100).

Sleep Difficulty Category	PSQI Score Range	N
No sleep difficulty	0	3
Mild sleep difficulty	0–7	24
Moderate sleep difficulty	8–14	44
Severe sleep difficulty	15–21	17
Total		100

5. Etiology of tinnitus: Sensorineural hearing loss (22%) and presbycusis (18%) were the leading etiologies, highlighting the age related and inner ear origins of chronic tinnitus (Table 5).

Graph 5: Distribution of study participants based on etiology.

Discussion

The study offers valuable insight into the clinical and psychological characteristics of chronic subjective tinnitus among patients in a tertiary care hospital. Most participants (61%) reported having tinnitus for less than a year, indicating early stage presentation in the majority. Similar trends were observed in an earlier research by Gudwani et al., where early symptom onset was associated with more favorable treatment responses and prognosis. [8] Sensorineural hearing loss was the most common audiological finding affecting 69% and 63% of patients in the right and left ears. This is consistent with existing literature, including studies by Song et al. and Alswiahb & Park, which reported high frequencies of cochlear or retrocochlear involvement in chronic tinnitus patients [1,2]. The prevalence of presbycusis and SNHL as the leading etiologies also reflects age related auditory decline as a major contributing factor, echoing findings in studies from both India and abroad.

In terms of psychological impact, 32% of participants experienced moderate handicap due to tinnitus. This is somewhat lower than figures reported by Kirsch et al., who found greater psychological burden, particularly in patients with low coping ability [4]. The absence of severe or catastrophic handicap levels in our participants may be attributed to early detection and consistent follow up. These findings reinforce the need for psychological assessment as part of a routine tinnitus management.

Sleep quality was another significant concern, with 97% of individuals reporting some degree of difficulty and more than 60% experiencing moderate to severe disturbances. These outcomes align with the COMiT-ID consensus study by Hall et al., which emphasized sleep disruption as one of the most distressing consequences of tinnitus and a key indicator for clinical monitoring. [11]

Etiological findings indicated that SNHL and presbycusis were the most common underlying causes, supporting previously established associations between inner ear damage and tinnitus. Psychogenic and metabolic factors also contributed, suggesting that both physical and psychological health influence tinnitus perception.

Overall, the study highlights the multifactorial nature of tinnitus and underscores the importance of early evaluation, hearing assessments and psychosocial support. The findings support a holistic approach that integrates audiological and mental health services to improve outcomes in patients with chronic subjective tinnitus.

Conclusion

The study emphasizes the complex nature of chronic subjective tinnitus, linking it to both audiological and psychological factors. The findings suggest that tinnitus severity correlates with psychological distress and sleep disturbances, highlighting the need for a comprehensive, multidisciplinary approach to treatment. Early diagnosis, thorough audiological assessments and psychological support can lead to better management and improved quality of life for patients suffering from tinnitus. Further research is needed to explore more effective therapeutic strategies for this debilitating condition.

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